

Interview Guide

Let's start by talking about your experience in identifying problems on your own:

1. How was your interaction with the catalog during the past week? Did you consult it again? If so, at what moment?
2. Did you use the catalog while developing any activity? If yes, how was it?
3. Have you been able to find more problems since our last meeting?

Now, talking about the problem identification process as a whole:

1. Did the catalog help or not help you identify problems in the architecture you work with? If yes, how? If not, why?
2. Are there problems you had not noticed or did not know about until you found them in the catalog? If yes, which ones?
3. Did the catalog help or not help you propose solutions for the identified problems? If yes, how? If not, why?
4. Do you have suggestions for new anti-patterns or for new solutions to the existing anti-patterns? If yes, which ones?
5. If you were to recommend the catalog to a colleague, how would you suggest they use it? And do you intend to use the catalog again yourself? In what way?
6. Did you identify any challenges and/or benefits when using the catalog during problem identification? Did you have any difficulty understanding any anti-pattern, whether the problem or the solution?
7. Finally, do you have any suggestions for improving the catalog? What other types of tools could help you in the development of Micro Frontends?